

PEER REVIEW REPORT

Peer review report for:

Galatti, L., Reis, F. B. dos, Mello, A. M de. (2025). Circular startups and the integration of social dimensions into business models. *RAE-Revista de Administração de Empresas*, 65(4), 2025. e2024-0174. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1590/S0034-759020250402>

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galatti, L., Reis, F. B. dos, Mello, A. M de. (2025). Peer review report for: Circular startups and the integration of social dimensions into business models. *RAE-Revista de Administração de Empresas*, 65(4), 2025. e2024-0174. Zenodo. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14606444>

Disclaimer: The content of the Peer Review Report is the full copy of the reviewers' and authors' reports. Typing and punctuation errors are not edited.

Reviewers:

The first reviewer did not authorize disclosure of their identity and peer review report.

Juan Felipe Espinosa-Cristia | ORCID: 0000-0002-5629-6328 | Universidad Técnica Federico Santa María, Valparaíso, Chile

ROUND 1

Reviewer 2 Report

Reviewer: Juan Felipe Espinosa-Cristia

Date review returned: 07-Aug-2024

Recommendation: Major Revision

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).

No conflict.

Comments to the Author

The article “CIRCULAR STARTUPS AND THE INTEGRATION OF SOCIAL DIMENSIONS INTO BUSINESS MODELS” presents a relevant study on the social impact of circular startups. Still, it could be improved in the following ways:

The argument overemphasizes novelty: The article repeatedly stresses that startups have a higher potential for social impact than established companies because of their inherent innovative nature. While this is a plausible argument, it lacks strong empirical backing within the article. Authors need to show this point in the data and not as a normative principle.

The study does not directly compare startups to established businesses, so this conclusion seems premature. Future research should either include a comparative analysis or soften this claim.

In terms of generalizability, the article recognizes its narrow focus on startups but does not fully address the limitations this poses on generalizing findings to other types of organizations. Expanding the discussion on how these findings might or might not apply to SMEs and multinational corporations would strengthen the argument.

Finally, in terms of the social dimension focus, the article focuses primarily on startups' intentions and declared practices concerning the social dimension, without a robust analysis of actual outcomes and impact achieved. This approach risks portraying a potentially overly positive image of startups' social performance without concrete evidence.

Analysis

- 1) *Lack of outcome-based data: The study heavily relies on company statements and publicly available information, lacking a robust analysis of demonstrable social outcomes. This reliance on self-reported data might lead to an overly optimistic portrayal of startups' social impact. Future research should incorporate more objective measures and data sources, such as impact reports, employee surveys, and community engagement assessments, to provide a more balanced and nuanced view of the actual social impact achieved.*
- 2) *Limited engagement with contrasting perspectives: While the article identifies a gap in the literature concerning the social dimension of circular economy in the Global South, it misses the opportunity to engage more deeply with the unique social and economic contexts of the region. This limits the depth of analysis and understanding of the specific challenges and opportunities faced by circular startups in these contexts.*
- 3) *Absence of critical reflection: While the article acknowledges limitations in data availability and the potential for social washing bias, it does not critically reflect on its positionality and potential biases. A more reflexive approach would strengthen the analysis and acknowledge the limitations inherent in any research.*

Potential Improvements

- A) *Broaden data sources: Incorporate data beyond company statements and websites, such as impact assessments, stakeholder interviews (employees, community members, beneficiaries), and financial data to assess the actual impact of social initiatives.*
- B) *Comparative analysis: Include established businesses in future research to assess whether startups truly have a higher potential for social impact or if this is an unsupported assumption.*
- C) *Deepen contextual analysis: Engage more deeply with the specific social and economic contexts of the Global South, exploring the unique challenges and opportunities for circular startups in these regions.*
- D) *Strengthen critical reflection: Acknowledge the limitations of the research, including potential biases and the difficulty of measuring social impact accurately.*

E) Develop a framework: Based on the identified patterns, create a framework that can guide circular startups in integrating social dimensions into their business models effectively.

If the authors address these limitations and incorporate these improvements, the article can make a more robust contribution to the understanding of the social dimension of circular economy and provide more practical guidance for startups and other organizations seeking to maximize their social impact.

Authors' responses

To Professor Juliana Bonomi and Fanny Saruchera. Vale

Editor in Chief and Associate Editor – RAE-Revista de Administração de Empresas

Submitted Manuscript “Circular startups and the integration of social dimensions into business models”

Dear Editors,

Firstly, we would like to extend our sincere thanks to the editorial team and the two anonymous reviewers for their insightful comments and detailed recommendations, which have greatly contributed to improving the quality of our paper.

We are pleased to submit the revised version of our manuscript, titled “Circular Startups and the Integration of Social Dimensions into Business Models,” for consideration in RAE – Revista de Administração de Empresas.

All the changes made to the manuscript have been highlighted in blue. We have also provided a detailed response to each comment from both the editors and reviewers. To facilitate cross-referencing, we have included the original questions or comments alongside a “Reply” column, where we summarize the modifications made in response.

We sincerely hope that the revisions meet your expectations and look forward to your feedback. Should you have any further questions or require additional clarifications, we would be happy to address them.

Thank you once again for your time and consideration.

Please do not hesitate to contact us if any further information is necessary.

Kind regards,

Yours Sincerely,

Reviewer A

Reviewer B

Comment: *Expresses concerns about the overemphasis on the novelty of startups' potential for social impact without strong empirical backing.*

Reply: *The research objective was rewritten to: “how Latin American circular startups incorporate the social dimension into their value propositions and operations,” to better contextualize the focus of the study. We removed the reference to social impact from the objective, as our research method does not allow for the measurement of impacts, as correctly pointed out by Reviewer B.*

Comment: Recommends that you either include a comparative analysis with established businesses or moderate this claim to avoid unsupported conclusions. The argument overemphasizes novelty: The article repeatedly stresses that startups have a higher potential for social impact than established companies because of their inherent innovative nature. While this is a plausible argument, it lacks strong empirical backing within the article. Authors need to show this point in the data and not as a normative principle.

Reply: We have better highlighted that the study is conducted within the context of circular startups, with the objective of understanding how the social dimension is incorporated into their strategies and operations. References to the higher potential of circular startups compared to other businesses have been removed. Therefore, the analysis is restricted to the context of circular startups, without considering social impacts in comparison to those of established businesses.

Comment: Notes the need to discuss the generalizability of your findings beyond startups, including implications for SMEs and multinational corporations.

Reply: The context of the study within circular startups has been emphasized throughout the text, and limitations of the study, particularly regarding the generalization of the results, have been added in the last two paragraphs of the conclusion.

Comment: Highlights the importance of moving beyond intentions and declared practices by incorporating a more robust analysis of actual social outcomes and impacts.

Reply: This information has been added as limitations of the study and suggestions for future research in the conclusion.

Comment: Suggests broadening your data sources to include impact assessments, stakeholder interviews, and other objective measures.

Reply: This information has been added as suggestions for future research in the conclusion, since the data we have does not allow for this kind of analysis.

Comment: Recommends a deeper engagement with the specific social and economic contexts of the Global South to provide a more nuanced analysis.

Reply: Important information about the Global South was added in the second-to-last paragraph of the introduction, the second-to-last paragraph of the “Circular Startups in the Global South” section, and the third paragraph of the conclusion to better contextualize our study in relation to this theme.

Comment: Recommends that you critically reflect on potential biases and limitations of your study, which would strengthen the research’s credibility.

Reply: The conclusion has been updated almost in its entirety, providing a clearer emphasis on the contributions, limitations, and suggestions for future research.

Comment: Suggests developing a framework based on your findings to guide circular startups in effectively integrating social dimensions into their business models.

Reply: Figure 4 has been added to illustrate a framework that summarizes the key findings, indicating potential directions for circular startups to develop the social dimension within their value propositions and operations.